

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND SIMPLIFIED MODEL OF TENSILE FAILURE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE UNDER HIGH STRAIN RATE

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ABSTRACT

A dynamic Monte Carlo numerical method considering the strain-rate effects of the constituents and the inertia effect is proposed to simulating the tensile failure process of unidirectional composite under impact. Based on the dynamic properties of the CF, GF fibres and Epoxy, the dynamic failure process of CF/Epoxy and GF/Epoxy is simulated. The numerical results is compared with the test results of unidirectional composites under tensile impact. The simulating results reveal the meso-scopic mechanism of the macroscopic dynamic properties of unidirectional composites.

Keywords: Unidirectional Composite, Monte Carlo Simulation, High Strain Rate

1. INTRODUCTION

Since last decade, many scholars searched dynamic properties of composites from experiments and theoretical analyses^[1,12], such as to use the Monte Carlo numerical simulating method of unidirectional composite under static loading to dynamic loading^[3,4,15]. The dynamic failure of composites is more complicated than static. There are not only the random failure of fibre-break, matrix-crack, interface-debonding, but the effects of rate-dependence of constituents and dynamic stress-concentration of broken fibres. The rate-dependence of constituents has not been accounted for dynamic Monte Carlo simulating method of unidirectional composites in the past, and internal friction after matrix-crack isn't considered. The difference between experimental results and numerical simulating results can't be explained well. In the present paper, based on the experimental results of fibres and matrix under tensile impact, the microessence for dynamic macro-properties of the composites are discussed.

2. DYNAMIC MONTE CARLO NUMERICAL SIMULATING METHOD

The unidirectional composite (Fig.1) consists of n fibres, and m meshes with Δx length ($m=L/\Delta x$, L length of fibre) are divided along fibre direction. According to shear-lag

model and considering inertia of fibres the dynamic differential equations of each fibre at the moment $t=k\Delta t$ ($k=0,1,2,\dots$, Δt is iso-step of time) are

$$\begin{aligned} EA \frac{d^2 u_{i,j}^k}{dx^2} + \frac{GH}{D} (u_{i-1,j}^k - 2u_{i,j}^k + u_{i+1,j}^k) &= \rho A \frac{d^2 u_{i,j}^k}{dt^2} & (1 < i < n) \\ EA \frac{d^2 u_{1,j}^k}{dx^2} + \frac{GH}{D} (u_{2,j}^k - u_{1,j}^k) &= \rho A \frac{d^2 u_{1,j}^k}{dt^2} & (i=1) \\ EA \frac{d^2 u_{n,j}^k}{dx^2} + \frac{GH}{D} (u_{n-1,j}^k - u_{n,j}^k) &= \rho A \frac{d^2 u_{n,j}^k}{dt^2} & (i=n) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where E, A, ρ are modulus, crosssection area, density of fibre separately, D is the distance of two neighbouring fibres, H is the thickness of composite, G is the shear modulus of matrix, $u_{i,j}^k$ is the displacement of node (i,j) . The left boundary is fixed, and the right moves with a constant speed v , namely

$$\begin{aligned} u_{1,j}^k &= u_{1,1}(k\Delta t) = 0 & (1 < i < n) \\ u_{i,m}^k &= u_{i,m}(k\Delta t) = V k \Delta t = u_0^k & (1 < i < n) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Substituting 2-order centric difference into 2-order differentials of Eqn.(2), that is^[9]

$$EA \frac{d^2 u_{i,j}^k}{dx^2} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} (u_{i,j-1}^k - 2u_{i,j}^k + u_{i,j+1}^k) & \text{(fibre unbroken)} \\ \frac{4}{3\Delta x^2} (u_{i,j-\frac{1}{2}}^k - u_{i,j-\frac{1}{2}}^k) & \text{(fibre from } (i,j) \text{ to } (i,j+1) \text{ break)} \\ \frac{4}{3\Delta x^2} (u_{i,j+\frac{1}{2}}^k - u_{i,j+\frac{1}{2}}^k) & \text{(fibre from } (i,j-1) \text{ to } (i,j) \text{ break)} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d^2 u_{i,j}^k}{dt^2} = \frac{1}{\Delta t^2} (u_{i,j}^{k+1} - 2u_{i,j}^k + u_{i,j}^{k-1}) \quad (4)$$

If matrix cracks, rewrite Eqn.(1) as

$$EA \frac{d^2 u_{i,j}^k}{dx^2} + \tau = \rho A \frac{d^2 u_{i,j}^k}{dt^2} \quad (5)$$

where

$$\tau = \begin{cases} \frac{GH}{D} (u_{i+1,j}^k - u_{i,j}^k) + H \tau_0 & \text{(matrix cracks between } (i-1,j) \text{ and } (i,j)) \\ \frac{GH}{D} (u_{i-1,j}^k - u_{i,j}^k) + H \tau_0 & \text{(matrix cracks between } (i-1,j) \text{ and } (i,j)) \\ H \tau_0 & \text{(matrix cracks at } i=1 \text{ or } i=n) \\ 2H \tau_0 & \text{(matrix cracks around fibre)} \end{cases}$$

where τ_0 is friction between fibre and matrix after matrix-crack.

The failure criteria of fibre and matrix should consist of the effect of strain rate. Tensile impact results and analyses of fibre bundles show^{(8), (17)} dynamic strength of fibres submits to Weibull distribution yet, and shape parameter β is rate independent, but scale parameter α is a function of strain rate. The dynamic Weibull function at strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ is

$$G(\Delta x, \sigma) = 1 - \exp(-\Delta x \alpha \sigma^\beta) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{\Delta x}}\right)^\beta\right]$$

$$\alpha = \alpha(\dot{\epsilon})$$

$$\sigma_{\Delta x} = \sigma_{\Delta x}(\dot{\epsilon}) = (L\alpha)^{-1/\beta}$$
(6)

According to Eqn.(6), the strength S_{ij} of fibre from node (i,j) to (i,j+1) are determined from the direct sampling method⁽⁸⁾. The failure criteria of fibre is

$$\frac{EA}{\Delta x} (u_{i,j+1}^k - u_{i,j}^k) > S_{ij} \quad (\text{fibre breaks})$$
(7)

The failure criteria of matrix is

$$\frac{GH}{D} (u_{i+1,j}^k - u_{i,j}^k) > \tau_m \quad (\text{matrix cracks})$$
(8)

where $\tau_m = \tau_m(\dot{\epsilon})$ is the ultimate shear stress of matrix under strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$. After matrix cracking, $\tau_c = \tau_m$.

Substituting Eqn.(1) to (8) with the dimensionless variables

$$\xi = \sqrt{\left(\frac{EAD}{GH}\right)}, \quad T = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\rho AD}{GH}\right)}, \quad \Delta X = \frac{\Delta x}{\xi}, \quad \Delta T = \frac{\Delta t}{T}, \quad U_{ij} = \frac{u_{ij}^k}{\xi}$$

and using the successive over-relaxation method⁽⁸⁾, $u_{i,j}^{k+1}$ can be obtained from $u_{i,j}^k$, $u_{i,j}^{k-1}$ and the boundary condition at $t=(k+1)\Delta t$. A dynamic Monte Carlo numerical simulating program DCOMP has been compiled for unidirectional composites in accordance with Eqn.(1)-(8) (Fig.2). The static program SCOMP can be got if the inertia term of Eqn.(1) is eliminated.

3. SIMULATING RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Determining parameters and checking program

Fig.3 shows the dynamic stress concentration of the fibre neighbouring the broken fibre follows change of time when a fibre breaks suddenly. As $\Delta T = \Delta X = 0.2$, the difference between calculated values and Hedgepeth's theoretical values⁽⁸⁾ is very small, but $\Delta T = \Delta X = 0.5$, the difference is rather large. Fig.3 explains that DCOMP program for calculating dynamic displacement field, strain field and stress field is correct. To describe stress field near the broken fibres accurately, steps ΔX and ΔT must be very small. In Ref.5,

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5 Failure Model of CF/Epoxy (Static)
(x - fibre breaks
· - matrix crack)

Fig. 6 Failure Model of CF/Epoxy (Dynamic)
(x - fibre breaks · - matrix crack)

it isn't suitable to select ineffective length as the space mesh step (corresponding to $\Delta X = 1$). $\Delta X = \Delta T = 0.2$ is considered to be suitable for the capacity and velocity of computer and the calculating accuracy.

3.2 Numerical Simulation of CF/Epoxy under tensile impact

It is known CF is rate insensitive^[9,17], and dynamic parameters are the same as static parameters which are selected from Ref.4. Epoxy is rate sensitive, and the parameters are selected from Ref.9. The parameters are in Table 1. Fig.4 is the static and dynamic stress-strain curves calculated with SCOMP and DCOMP programs. Fig. 5 and 6 are the failure modes. Fig 4,5,6 show the stress-strain curves and failure modes of CF/Epoxy are rate independent. It coincides with the test results^[11]. Hence, the rate insensitivity of CF/Epoxy are decided by CF, moreover, the stress-strain curve and failure mode are little affected by inertia effect, i.e. dynamic stress concentration.

Table 1 CF and Epoxy parameters

Crosssection of fibre A(mm ²)	3.85x10 ⁻⁵	
Volume fraction of fibre V _f (%)	60	
Modulus of CF (Gpa)	230.3	
Shape parameter β	6.98	
Scale parameter σ_c (GPa)	4.32*	4.36**
ξ (mm)	0.0634*	0.0590**
T(μ s)		0.00541**
Shear modulus of epoxy G(GPa)	0.98*	1.13**
Ultimate shear stress of epoxy τ_m (GPa)	0.0308*	0.0595**

* Static, ** Dynamic (strain rate = 500 1/s)

3.3 Numerical Simulation of GF/Epoxy under tensile impact

GF is rate sensitive^[7]. Both static and dynamic parameters are from Ref.7 (see Table 2). Parameters of epoxy show on Tab.1. Fig.7 shows the stress-strain curves, Fig.8, 9 show the failure modes.

Table 2 GF parameters

Crosssection of fibre A(mm ²)	2.37x10 ⁻⁵	
Volume fraction of fibre V _f (%)	65	
Modulus of GF (Gpa)	62.8*	70.5**
Shape parameter β	10.4	
Scale parameter σ_c (GPa)	2.50*	6.35**
ξ (mm)	0.0210*	0.0207**
T(μ s)		0.00394**

* Static, ** Dynamic (strain rate = 500 1/s)

From Fig.7 both simulated and experimental dynamic unstable strain (corresponding to

the maximum stress) is rather larger than the experimental static unstable strain. It explains the high speed toughness of GF is one of the important factors to result in the high speed toughness of GF/Epoxy. From Fig.7 the maximum stress of calculated $\sigma - \epsilon$ curve is larger than the test result, the unstable strain is smaller than the test result. It also shows that the rate sensitivity of GF and the dynamic Monte Carlo numerical simulation cannot explain the nonlinearity of tested $\sigma - \epsilon$ curve of GF/Epoxy

Fig. 7

The $\sigma - \epsilon$ curve from DCOMP is little higher than that from SCOMP (shown on Fig.7). It means inertia effect brings out the nonlinearity of stress strain curve, however, the level is very low. The inertia has little influence on the failure mode of GF/Epoxy under dynamic loading too.

According to Fig.5,6,8,9, matrix failure in CF/Epoxy is little under impact and fracture is even, matrix failure in GF/Epoxy is obvious and fracture is irregular. These coincide with the test results^[1,12]. It explains failure mode is decided by fibre toughness. The larger the fibre toughness, the more the matrix failure, the more irregular the fracture .

Fig. 8 Failure Model of GF/Epoxy (SCOMP)
(x - fibre breaks . - matrix crack)

Fig. 9 Failure Model of GF/Epoxy (DCOMP)
(x - fibre breaks . - matrix crack)

4. Conclusions and discussion

(1) The present paper finds a dynamic Monte Carlo simulating method for the unidirectional composite which considers the rate effects of constituents and inertia effect, and reveal the meso-scope mechanism of macroscopic dynamic properties of unidirectional composite founded on simulating the dynamic deformation process until failure based on the parameters of constituents.

(2) Numerical simulation shows dynamic properties of fibres in unidirectional composite are principal. Rate sensitivity of fibre decides that of unidirectional composite. For dynamic stress-strain curves and failure modes, effect of inertia is slight. Toughness of fibre decides the failure mode of unidirectional composite.

(3) Rate sensitivity of GF can not explain the nonlinearity of dynamic stress strain curve of GF/Epoxy. In fact, energy dissipation is accompanied with the deformation and failure process under impact. From the experiments of immediate temperature of fibre bundles under tensile impact, strain energy at fibre breaking transforms heat^[9]. Hence a local immediate high temperature field must appear due to fibre breaking on microstructure level. GF is temperature dependent^[10]. Therefore local immediate high temperature must affect the stress field, and decreases the load bearing of fiber near the broken fiber. Thus thermo-mechanic interaction is caused and influences the dynamic stress-strain curve. Because the thermo-mechanic coupling has not been considered in the dynamic Monte Carlo simulation, the difference between the experimental stress-strain curve and that of numerical results for GF/Epoxy cannot be explained well. CF is temperature independent^[10], so thermo-mechanic interaction does not exist. Then, the test results coincide with the numerical results.

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